

INTERNAL AUDITING AS A PANACEA TO POOR CORPORATE GOVERNANCE

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Abstract

Internal audit is the main driver of corporate governance. It is seen as an indispensable factor in ensuring sound financial reporting which increases the confidence between managers and other stakeholders. The aim of this paper is to have a critical review of related literature to unveil the impact of internal auditing on corporate governance. Another aim is to offer empirical evidence on the roles of internal auditing in enhancing the corporate governance in some companies in Nigeria. Internal auditing promotes corporate governance and its relationship to internal audit process. The paper revealed that internal auditing is an important part of the success of corporate governance, hence seen as a management tool for a successful corporate governance. It was also revealed that internal audit has a strong link that encourages value increase of an organization and its objectives. It was concluded that interactions between audit committee and internal audit help to boost corporate governance. It was recommended that internal audit increases the financial information quality and ensures the validity of financial reporting.